

Comparative assessment of phytochemical constituents using leaves and bark of *Dalbergia sissoo* and *Cordia myxa*

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ABSTRACT

Numerous healthy plants possess medical properties that are a result of chemical elements contained within them. Numerous phytochemicals perform a number of functions that aid in boosting the immune system and providing immunity against chronic illness, thereby protecting the body from hazardous infections. The primary objective of this study is to characterize the phytochemical elements of therapeutic plants found in and around Bahawalpur. Flavonoids, tannin, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, steroids, proteins, carbohydrates, saponin, glycosides, and alkaloids are all chemical components found in plants that are extremely important to their survival. The name of plants that are used for examine the phytochemical tests are *Cordia myxa* and *Dalbergia sissoo*. Ethanolic and aqueous extracts of leaves and bark are used for the assessment of various phytochemicals present in these plants. Tannins, saponins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, proteins, steroids, terpenoids and phenols all are present in the selected plants. However reducing sugar, steroids, tannins and glycoside are absent in *Cordia myxa* extracts and terpenoids, saponins and reducing sugar are absent in *Dalbergia sissoo*.

Keywords: Phytochemical constituents, Comparative assessment, Leaves, Bark

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are the universe's oldest surviving entire health care system (Umair et al., 2017; Saeed et al., 2022). Green chemistry is an expert and initial platform for the discovery of natural medicines. Physiologically active supplies of medication are significant organic ingredients (Saleh et al., 2009). Today, 80 percent of the 120 active chemicals extracted from higher plants that are commonly utilized in contemporary medicine demonstrate a good connection among its advanced medicinal applications and the evolutionary history of the plants from which they are derived (Fabricant and Daniel, 2001).

The usage of medicinal plants, including fresh or dried parts, entire, sliced, and powdered or a progressive form of the plant commonly made through withdrawal with different solvents, plays a vital function and begins the backbone of the regular medication in most outmoded systems of cure (Mukherjee, 1986). Nowadays, well-known plants that naturally combine and accumulate secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, tannins, glycosides, volatile oils, minerals, and vitamins retain therapeutic qualities (Abuga, I., Sulaiman et al., 2021).

Dalbergia sissoo is a moderate to massive leafy tree, commonly called as sisu in Pakistan, sheesham, tahli, tali or jag in various parts of the world. It is most frequently used to diagnose sore throats, diarrhea, syphilis, and gonorrhoea. It's being used to treat disorders such as blood purification, headaches, leprosy, inflammations, infections, bronchitis, hernias, and skin ailments (Mannan et al., 2017). The leaf extract is used to treat anthelmintic, eye, nasal disorders, scabies, burning sensations, scalding urine, and digestive problems (Saha et al., 2013).

The genus *Cordia* (Boraginaceae family) contains shrubs, leaves, bark and fruits that are extensively dispersed in warmer climates. Several chemicals with diverse bioactivities, such as flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, alkaloids, and fatty acids, were isolated from various *Cordia* species plant sections. The stem, bark, and leaves of the plant are employed in several indigenous systems of medicine such as Ayurveda and Unani and are popular among diverse ethnic groups in India for the treatment of a number of maladies as an astringent, anthelmintic, diuretic, antidiabetic, anti-diabetic, and expectorant (Jasiem *et al.*, 2016). Leaves and stem bark have been used for centuries to treat dyspepsia, fever, diarrhea, leprosy, gonorrhoea, and burning sensation. In Pakistan, the leaves are used as a diuretic and demulcent (Kumar and Khurana, 2016).

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

1. Phytochemical analysis of leaves and bark of *cordia myxa*.
2. Assessment of phytochemicals in the leaves and bark of *Dalberia sissoo*.
3. Comparative assessment of the leaves and bark of *Dalberia sissoo* and *Cordia myxa*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

SAMPLE COLLECTION AND STUDY AREA

Dalbergia sissoo Roxb. and *Cordia myxa L.* grow in Pakistan's various regions. The plant sample of selected species (leaves and Bark) was collected from the village of Tehsil Ahmad Pur East District Bahawalpur (Altaf, 2022) on November 5th, 2020 (Figure 1, and 2). The plant materials were taxonomically identified and confirmed by the “Department of Forestry, Range and Wildlife Management of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur”.

PREPARATION OF AQUEOUS AND ETHANOLIC EXTRACT

The plant materials were thoroughly rinsed with tap water twice and then dried in the shade until all of the water molecules were evaporated and the plant was dry enough to grind. After dryness, the plant components will now be ground into a fine powder with a mechanical blender and kept in sealed plastic bags labeled for future usage (Figure 3).

AQUEOUS EXTRACT

In 200 ml of distilled water, 20 gram of material was suspended. After 30 minutes of extraction at 70°C, the extracts were filtered using Filter paper (whatman No.1. After evaporating the extracts at 45 ° C to form a paste, it was transferred to sterile vials and stored until use (Figure 4, and 5).

ETHANOLIC EXTRACTS

In 20 gram of material, 95 percent ethanol was added. After 72 hours at 27 ° C, the extraction was filtered using Filter paper (whatman No.1. After evaporating the extracts at 45 ° C

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

The phytochemical identification is performed on a plant extract which is obtained by solvent extraction using a particular standard procedure (Yadav *et al.*, 2011).

Figure 1: Collection of plant sample.

Figure 2: Procedure dry leaves.

Figure 3: Powder of *Dalbergia sissoo* Roxb. and *Cordia myxa* L. leaves

Figure 4: Aqueous extract leaves.

Figure 5: Aqueous extract Bark.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

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Proteins Test

Millon's Test

When 2ml of Millon's reagent was mixed with raw extract, it produced a white precipitate that turned red when heated. As a result, the existence of protein has been verified.

Ninhydrin Test

When crude extract was boiled with 2ml of 0.2 percent Ninhydrin solution, the violet color is appeared which confirmed the presence of amino acid and proteins.

TEST FOR CARBOHYDRATES

Felling's Test

Crude extract is combined with an equal volume (2ml) of Fehling A and Fehling B reagents and lightly boiled. The presence of carbohydrates was measured by the appearance of brick red precipitate at the bottom of the test tube (reducing sugars).

Iodine Test

The crude extract was combined with 2 ml of iodine solution. The reducing sugar's ability was shown by a purple or dark blue hue (carbohydrates).

Test for Tannins

The raw extract was mixed with a FeCl_3 solution at a concentration of 2%. The presence of tannins was determined by a black / blue-green color.

Lead Acetate Test

5 ml of aqueous extract and few drops of 10% lead acetate solution were mixed. White precipitate were formed which indicate the presence of tannins.

FLAVONOIDES TEST

Shinoda Test

Combine the raw extract with a few drops of concentrated HCl and a few pieces of magnesium ribbon to create a paste-like consistency. The presence of flavonoids was detected after a few minutes by the appearance of a pink florid hue on the surface of the solution.

Alkaline Reagent Test

The crude extract was treated with 2 ml of a NaOH solution containing 2 percent sodium hydroxide. When adding a sprinkle of diluted acid, the presence of flavonoids was verified by the formation of an excessive yellow hue that became colorless after the acid was removed.

Test for Saponins

When the raw extract was combined with 5ml of distilled water (H_2O) and forcefully shaken, the result was a clear liquid. During the construction/production of balanced foam, it was shown that saponins existed.

GLYCOSIDES TEST

Keller-Kilani Test

It was necessary to combine the raw extract with 2 mL glacial acetic acid that included 1-2 drops of FeCl₃ solution at a concentration of 2 percent before pouring the mixture into another test tube. It was discovered that cardiac glycosides were present when a brown ring formed in the middle of the test tube was formed.

RESULTS

The *Cordia myxa L.* and *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb* plants extracts of barks and leaves were investigated for the qualitative phytochemical screenings (Table 1). The methanol extracts investigation showed positive result in many constituent in all samples. The, saponins, reducing sugar, amino acid and carbohydrates were present in all four samples and showed positive results. While soluble protein, carbohydrates were absent in bark and leaves. Tannins are only present in bark. Flavonoids are present in all except bark. Alkaloids were present in bark. The current analysis showed that the selected tree species are characterized with the presence of various phytochemicals. As per the results the specie and plant parts has statistically significant $p < 0.05$ effect on plant extraction yield. However, the solvent type had statistically non-significant $p > 0.05$ effect on plant extraction yield (Table 2).

Table 1: Plant Sample.

Sr.	Botanical name	Common name	Plant part used
1	<i>Dalbergia sisso Roxb.</i>	Sheesham	Leaves and Bark
2	<i>Cordia myxa L.</i>	Lassurah	Leaves and Bark

Table 2: Yield of palnt extraction in different solvents.

Plant name	Plant part	Extract	Yield
<i>Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.</i>	Leaves	Ethanol	20.02 ± 2.1
		Aqueous	23.17 ± 2.12
	Bark	Ethanol	15.31 ± 2.82
		Aqueous	19.12 ± 2.80
<i>Cordia myxa L.</i>	Leaves	Ethanol	18.10 ± 0.70
		Aqueous	17.03 ± 0.77
	Bark	Ethanol	12.02 ± 0.75
		Aqueous	11.05 ± 0.73

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF *CORDIA MYXA L.* EXTRACT OF LEAVES AND BARK

The experimental work is start by extraction of leaves and bark of *Cordia myxa L.* with distilled water and ethanol. Table 3 demonstrated that following tests are performed. These phytochemical tests shows the following results that are involved the presence of alkaloids, saponins, carbohydrates, starch, proteins and flavonoids, but reducing sugar, tannins, and glycoside are absent.

Table 3: Phytochemical analysis of *cordia myxa l.* Extract of leaves and bark.

Sr.	Test Name	EXTRACT	TEST REAGENT	OBSERVATION	LEAVES	BARK
1	Alkaloids	1 % HCl	Wagner's reagent	Deep purple ppt	+	+
2	Tannins	Ethanol	10% lead acetate	White ppt	-	-
3	Glycosides	H ₂ O	10% Lead acetate	No change in color	-	-
4	Saponins	H ₂ O	Distilled water	Forthing	+	+
5	Flavonoids	Ethanol	Mg and conc. HCl	Brown colour	+	+
6	Proteins	H ₂ O	Ninhydrin solution	violet color	+	+
7	Carbohydrates	H ₂ O	10% α Naphthol+ H ₂ SO ₄	Red ring	+	+
8	Starch	H ₂ O	Iodine sol.	Blue color	+	+

(+) = present: (-) = absent:

PHYTOCHEMICALS EXAMINE OF THE EXTRACTS OF *DALBERGIA SISSOO ROXB.* LEAVE AND BARK

Preliminary phytochemical investigation of ethanol and aqueous extracts of bark and leaves of *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* tree shows that alkaloids, tannins, carbohydrates, starch, proteins, glycosides and flavonoids are present, but reducing sugar and saponins are absent.

TABLE 4: PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE EXTRACTS OF *DALBERGIA SISSOO ROXB.* LEAVES AND BARK

Sr.	Test Name	EXTRACT	TEST REAGENT	OBSERVATION	LEAVES	BARK
1	Alkaloids	1 % HCl	Wagner's reagent	Deep purple ppt	+	+
			Dradendroff's reagent	Deep purple ppt	+	+
2	Tannins	Ethanol	10% lead acetate solution	White ppt	+	+
3	Glycosides	H ₂ O	10% Lead acetate solution	No change in color	+	+
			2 ml of CCl ₃ and 2 ml of conc. H ₂ SO ₄	reddish brown color	+	+
4	Saponins	H ₂ O	Distilled water	Forthing	-	-
5	Flavonoids	Ethanol	Mg and conc. HCl	Brown colour	+	+
6	Proteins	H ₂ O	Ninhydrin solution	violet color	+	+
7	Carbohydrate s	H ₂ O	10% α Naphthol+ H ₂ SO ₄	Red ring	+	+
	Reducing sugar	H ₂ O	Benedict's reagent	No change in colour	-	-
8	Starch	H ₂ O	Iodine sol.	Blue color	+	+

(+) = present: (-) = absent:

COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF PHYTOCHEMICALS IN *DALBERGIA SISSOO ROXB* AND *CORDIA MYXA L.* IN LEAVES AND BARK

Comparative assessment of phytochemicals in *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* and *Cordia myxa L.* leaves and bark showed that following phytochemicals like alkaloids (purple colour ppt) are present in both samples (Table 4). Tannins give blue green colour in extracts of leaves and bark of selected tree species of *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* but absent in *Cordia myxa L.* Glycosides are absent in *Cordia myxa L.* leaves and bark and present in *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* leaves and bark. No change in color confirmed the presence of glycosides. Frothing in extract of leaves and bark of *Cordia myxa L.* shows the presence of saponins, but it is absent in *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.*

samples. Brown colour in both samples confirms the presence of Flavonoids. Red ring shows carbohydrates in leaves and bark of both trees but some reducing sugars are absent in both parts of trees (Table 5).

Table 5: Comparative assessment of phytochemicals in *dalbergia sissoo roxb.* and *cordia myxa l.* In leaves and bark

Sr. No	Test	<i>Cordia Myxa L.</i>		<i>Dalbrgia Sisoo Roxb.</i>		Comparison
		Bark	Leave	Bark	Leave	
1	Alkaloids	+	+	+	+	Results showed that alkaloids (purple colour ppt) are present in both leaves and bark of both samples.
2	Tannins	-	-	+	+	Tannins give blue green colour which is present only in <i>Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.</i> but absent in other.
3	Glycosides	-	-	+	+	Glycosides are absent in <i>Cordia myxa L.</i> leaves and bark and present in <i>Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.</i> leaves and bark. No change in color confirmed the presence of glycosides.
4	Saponins	+	+	-	-	Frothing in extract of leaves and bark of <i>Cordia myxa L.</i> shows the presence of saponins, but it is absent in <i>Dalbergia sissoo Roxb</i> samples.
5	Flavonoids	+	+	+	+	Brown colour in both samples confirms the presence of Flavonoids.
6	Proteins	+	+	+	+	Violet colour in test showed the presence of proteins in both tree samples.
7	Carbohydrates	+	+	+	+	Red ring shows carbohydrates in leaves and bark of both trees but some reducing sugars are absent in both parts of trees.

DISCUSSION

Plants have been used for many years for a number of goals all over the world. Given the growing use of plant extracts in the pharmaceutical industry, determining their function and isolating/characterizing active compounds is critical. The phytochemical constituents of plants decide their medicinal properties (Ezeonu, and Ejikeme 2016). Proteins, carbohydrates, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolics, tannins, saponins, steroids, glycosides, and terpenes are some of the essential phytochemicals that are found in different sections of plants (Madike, L. N., Takaidza, S., and Pillay, M. (2017).

In preliminary phytochemical study, alkaloids, saponins, phenolic compounds, tannins, steroids and terpenoids were present in leaves and barks *Cordia myxa L.* but reducing sugar, glycoside and cyanogenic glycoside were absent (Parmar, 1998; Mahour 2008; Jamkhande et al., 2013; Nazim & Kakoti, 2013). Recent study shows that the experimental work is start by extraction of leaves and bark of *Cordia myxa L.* with distilled water and ethanol. Phytochemical tests shows the following results that are involved the presence of alkaloids, saponins, carbohydrates, starch, proteins and flavonoids, but reducing sugar, tannins, and glycoside are absent.

The phytochemical screening test of *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* stem include a series of presence or absence of following phytochemicals as carbohydrates, sugars, saponins, proteins, flavanoids, triterpenoids, tannins, alkaloids, steroids, amino acids, fats and oils (Parvesh Devi,

Sushila Singh, Promila, *et al.*, 2019). As per our findings preliminary phytochemical investigation of ethanol and aqueous extracts of bark and leaves of *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* tree shows that alkaloids, tannins, carbohydrates, starch, proteins, glycosides and flavonoids are present, but reducing sugar and saponins are absent.

CONCLUSION

The current investigation supported a variety of phytochemical elements found in *Cordia myxa L.* and *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.* plants taken from the village of Ahmad Pur East in the district of Bahawalpur. The leaves and bark of plants are used in the analysis. The research presented in this dissertation is carried out at the laboratories of The Islamia University of Bahawalpur's Department of Chemistry and Biochemistry. The presence of phytochemical analysis is determined in plant extracts, aqueous and ethanolic solutions using the conventional procedures. The phytochemical analysis showed that a mixture of phytochemicals as glycoside, carbohydrates (reducing sugar), flavonoids, tannins, saponins, proteins and alkaloids have all been discovered throughout the leaves and bark extracts of selected plants. Alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids, phenolic compounds (phenols), carbohydrates, starch, proteins and flavonoids are present in leaves and bark of *Cordia myxa L.* plant, but reducing sugar, steroids, tannins, and glycoside are absent. Alkaloids, tannins, carbohydrates, starch, proteins, glycosides and flavonoids are present in *Dalbergia sissoo Roxb.*, but reducing sugar, terpenoids and saponins are absent.

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